

Fatigue behaviour of $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated glassfibre/epoxy composite laminates used in wind turbine blades

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Abstract

Wind turbines are used widely to generate 'clean' electricity. However, wind turbine components and more specifically blades are suffering from various problems. One of them is fatigue. These wind blades are mainly manufactured using composite materials, and the present study investigates how their fatigue life could be prolonged by optimizing the fibre architecture..

Normally, $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated glass fibre-reinforced plastic (GFRP) layups are selected as skin materials due to their higher shear stiffness and toughness, which leads to the main focus in this paper. All the laminates have been manufactured by using the Vacuum bagging and the Resin Infusion Process. Tensile and torsion static test were performed to measure the stiffness and strength properties. A video extensometer was used to obtain the tensile stress-strain response in static tensile test, the Digital Imaging Correlation was employed to capture the strain field across the whole specimen gauge length and identify manufactured induced imperfections, 'hot spots', that could trigger damage in the form of resin cracking and delaminations. Tension-Tension fatigue tests were performed to obtain the S-N curves in addition to more complex loads such as Tension-Torsion fatigue tests that can substantially reduce the fatigue life of the wind turbine blade. Results for three different $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated GRFP composite laminates are reported.

Introduction

Wind turbines have been used for generating electricity due to their green energy supply, relatively fast installation, and low operation, low maintenance cost, high technological maturity, good infrastructure that lead to cost competitiveness of

such systems [1, 2]. Wind energy is expected to play an increasingly important role in the future national energy scene [1].

Composites are mainly chosen as wind turbine component materials because of their low density and excellent mechanical properties combination of strength and stiffness. Also, composites in general demonstrate better fatigue properties than metals when used in blade construction.

Wind turbine blade failures when in service are due to various complicated reasons. Table .1 lists some common factors that can cause such failures. As expected, the blade failure accounts for the most accidents and damage to the wind turbines of 23%, which in this paper will be analysed from the basic point of view of materials rather than structures.

Factors	Percentage
Blade failure	23%
Fire	19%
Structural failure	12%
Fatal accidents	9%
Environmental damage	9%
Transport	6%
Human injury	5%
Ice rainfall	4%
Other	13%

Table .1 Failure types of wind turbine accidents [3].

A typical wind turbine blade when in service is subject to flexural bending that induces tensile and compressive stresses and torsion that leads to development of shear stresses. Beside these, the wind blade must endure several orders of magnitude more cycles of fatigue loading than an aircraft, which makes wind turbines fatigue critical

structures. In this paper, the tension fatigue loading and the combination of tension and torsion loading are of main concern.

In order to obtain the fatigue failure pattern and fatigue life both for T-T (Tension-Tension) and T-Tor (Tension-Torsion), static and fatigue tests were performed for three different $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated GFRP composite laminates, which are $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$, $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$, $[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ respectively. Static strength and stiffness properties of these layups were obtained.

Experiments

Specimen preparation

All the $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated GFRP composite laminates were produced from with non-crimp E-glass fabric and epoxy resin, using Vacuum Bagging technique and Resin Infusion Process. The chosen layups are $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$, $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$, $[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ which is shown in Figure .1. The Vacuum Bagging and Resin Infusion System are illustrated in Figures .2 and 3.

Fig .1 Selected layups (90° & 0° in the quad-axial fabric were rotated from the bi-axial fabric) .

Fig .2 Illustration of vacuum bagging [4].

Fig .3 Illustration of resin Infusion System [5].

Mechanical testing

The mentioned quasi-static and fatigue tests were both performed on Instron Machines located in the Northwest Composite Centre, University of Manchester. For T-T fatigue test, load control was chose with a stress ratio $R=0.1$, according to ASTM standards. The testing frequency was chosen to be 2Hz since when higher frequency is applied the temperature of specimen surface is increased dramatically within few minutes. For T-Tor (tension-torsion) fatigue, angle control instead of torque control was chosen in the rotary aspect, the torsional amplitudes were 36° , 27° , 18° , and 9° , respectively. Finally, the Tor-Tor fatigue test differs from the other two since the specimen doesn't break into two parts, but delaminates extensively. Thus, a 50% drop in torque (indicated reduction in torsion rigidity) was defined as ultimate failure and ending the tests.

Torsion static tests

Figure .4 shows a typical static torsion testing. Loading-unloading testing procedure was chosen to be performed since there is no specific ASTM testing standard for the static torsion test. The specimen was twisted up to a maximum angle at a constant rate of 0.5 deg/s and then unloaded. The value of the applied twisting angle was increased gradually from 9° to 18° , 27° , 36° and 45° . In addition, a certain constant tensile load was applied during the torsion loading-unloading procedure. The torsional rigidity can be calculated from equations (1) and (2).

Fig .4 Typical static torsion test in process.

Torsional rigidity, GJ [6]

$$GJ = \frac{M_t L}{\omega} \quad (1)$$

$$GJ = G_{xy} \beta(c) b h^3$$

$$\beta(c) = \frac{32c^2}{\pi^4} \sum_{k=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \left\{ 1 - \frac{2c}{k\pi} \tan\left(\frac{k\pi}{2c}\right) \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$c = \frac{b}{h} \sqrt{\frac{G_{zx}}{G_{xy}}}$$

M_t = Torque

ω = twist angle (rad) per unit length
($\omega = \pi\theta/180$)

L= length of coupon (between grips)

b = width of coupon

h= thickness of coupon

G_{xy} / G_{zx} = In-plane and out-of-plane shear moduli

DIC technique

In mechanical testing of structural materials usually electrical strain gauges or clip gauges are used to measure specimen deformation. Such measurements give strain at a point or average strains with the danger of debonding or movement of the gauge. One of the strain acquisition methods, which became

widely applied in recent years due to development of PC computers and devices [7, 8], is Digital Imaging Correlation (DIC). This is a full-field image analysis method based on grey value digital images that can obtain the surface contour and displacement information of an object. Prepared with stochastic intensity pattern on the specimen surface, the position of each point in series of image can be identified by applying a correlation algorithm. Figure .5 shows image correlation as a displacement mapping technique, which the two images obtained at different strains are divided into sub-regions.

The simplified correlation algorithm is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} x^* &= x + u + (\partial u / \partial x) dx + (\partial u / \partial y) dy \\ y^* &= y + v + (\partial v / \partial x) dx + (\partial v / \partial y) dy \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

point (x_i, y_j) is undeformed and point (x_i^*, y_j^*) is deformed: u and v are translations of the centre of the sub-image in the X and Y directions. The distances are denoted by dx and dy .

Fig .5 Image correlation as a displacement mapping technique [9].

In this paper, the DIC technique was used to measure the strain field for three laminates under

tensile loading. The specimen was speckle sprayed and more than 500 photos for each laminate were taken by high-speed camera. This correlates the displacement of speckle to the strain on the surface of the specimen. Figure .6 shows specimens with speckles which were ready for DIC analysis.

Fig .6 Specimens speckled with white & black paints.

Fig .7a Torque-Angle curves of $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ laminate.

Results & discussion

Torsion static results

Torque-Angle curves were generated from the loading-unloading processes which are shown in Figure .7. Hysteresis loops are apparent during the loading-unloading process. According to equation (1), the slope of torque-angle curve stands for the torsional rigidity, which decreased apparently with the twist amplitude. The GJ (torsional rigidity) calculated from the Torque-Angle curves for the three different $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated GFRP composite laminates are shown in Figure .8 for both axial load $P=0$ (pure static torsion) and $P=50\% \sigma_{ult}$ ($50\% \sigma_{ult}$ were applied in addition of static torsion load). From observations, the $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ shows best GJ in static torsion load, $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ shows best GJ in combined loads. Also, increase of GJ (torsional rigidity) with P (tensile axial load) is dependent on the amount of 0° fibres.

Fig .7b Torque-Angle curves of $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates.

Fig .7c Torque-Angle curves of $[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates.

Fig .8 Torsional rigidities for $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated GFRP composite laminates under static torsion tests.

DIC results

Hundreds of photos were taken for each laminate under tensile test and the displacement information had been correlated to the strain concentration information within the gauge area. Figure .9 lists all the strain distribution for three $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated GFRP composite laminates under tensile tests.

From Figure .9a we can see that the higher strain concentrated in the gauge length area on both $\pm 45^\circ$ direction and final failure occurred at the maximum strain area with highlighted mark. In addition, the laminates experienced large elongation during test which shows ductile fracture behaviour.

For Figures .9b and c, the high strain occurred in gauge area dispersedly and the final failure fractured at the maximum strain spot area although hadn't been concentrated in certain large area. Both $[\pm 45^\circ / 0^\circ]_{2s}$ and $[\pm 45^\circ / 90^\circ / 0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates shown brittle fracture behaviour since they experienced quite small amount of elongation.

Fig .9a DIC images of strain distribution for a $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ laminate loaded in tension.

Fig .9b DIC images of strain distribution for a $[\pm 45^\circ / 0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminate loaded in tension.

Fig .9c DIC images of strain distribution for a $[\pm 45^\circ / 90^\circ / 0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminate loaded in tension.

Typical laminates failure

Different failure patterns and failure areas for the three $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated GFRP composite laminates are shown in Figure 10. It can be observed that $[\pm 45^\circ / 0^\circ]_{2s}$ and $[\pm 45^\circ / 90^\circ / 0^\circ]_{2s}$ experienced explosive failure in the middle of the gauge length, while the $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ failed when loaded under static tension or T-T fatigue but it didn't separate into two parts. For the T-Tor fatigue failure, almost complete delamination happened along the entire specimen, whereas the delamination was more localised under T-T fatigue.

Fig .10a Typical final failure of $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ laminates.

Fig .10b Typical final failure of $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates.

Fig .10c Typical final failure of $[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates

S-N curves

S-N curves were generated from long term T-T fatigue tests for $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated GFRP composite laminates and are shown in Figure.11. From observations, the T-T fatigue properties of $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$, $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$, $[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates begin to show a remarkable N_f decrease when cycled at 45% , 40% , 35% of ultimate static strength, respectively.

Fig .11 T-T fatigue of $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated laminates.

The combinations of T-Tor (Tension-Torsion) fatigue load were applied as well. The S-N curves are illustrated in Figures .12-a, b, c for $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$, $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$, $[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ respectively. Basically, the torsional cyclic load has reduced the fatigue life in certain stress level for all three laminates.

Fig .12a T-Tor & T-T fatigue of $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ laminates.

Fig .12b T-Tor &T-T fatigue of $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates.

Fig .12c T-Tor &T-T fatigue of $[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates.

From observation, $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ laminates shows the most decrease in fatigue life for T-Tor cyclic loading, and $[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ shows the least in the contrast. According to Figure .12-a and b, torsional cyclic load has diminished the fatigue limit of T-T s-N curves for the $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ laminate and $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates, and this feature is rather distinct for the $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ laminates. Whereas, the fatigue limits of T-Tor S-N curves maintain the original trend of T-T S-N one for $[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates.

In addition, the reduced fatigue life strongly depends on the twist angle, which needs further data analysis to transfer the angle information to shear stress and correlation this stress information and reduce fatigue life.

Conclusion

All the $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated GFRP composite laminates fracture within the gauge length under tensile loading. The $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ and $[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates showed brittle like fracture behaviour, whereas the $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ laminates fracture in a more ductile behaviour. The $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ laminates show the best GJ (torsional rigidity) when loaded statically in torsion only, while the $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates show best GJ under biaxial loading. Under T-T cyclic loading conditions, the $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates perform best in fatigue. The torsional cyclic load has diminished the “fatigue limit” of T-T S-N curves for $[\pm 45^\circ]_{4s}$ laminates. The T-Tor S-N curves of $[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates maintain the original trend of T-T fatigue properties. The reduced fatigue life depends on the applied twist angle

Future work

In the next stage of our research, focus will be on accomplishing the Tor-Tor fatigue tests to get the pure torsional fatigue properties. In the meantime, the data analysis and stress calculation need to be put into main concern to quantify the influence of torsional cyclic load on T-Tor S-N curve, and also in order to specify the role of 0° and 90° layers in the damage pattern for $\pm 45^\circ$ dominated composite laminates. Besides, much work on the fatigue model is necessary to identify a suitable failure criterion to predict the fatigue life.

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